

Helena Geisler | In cooperation with Doerte Hinrichsen

Survey of student applicants at a German art academy

English questionnaire

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Research project:	Survey of applicants for the Bachelor of Fine Arts at the Academy of Fine Arts “Hochschule für bildende Künste Hamburg” (Master's thesis by Helena Geisler)
Field time questionnaire:	March 23 to 29, 2020

CONTENT

Description	1
Questionnaire structure.....	2
Notice in the online application	5
Welcome message	6
Privacy policy.....	7
Section A: Matching.....	8
Section B: Application.....	10
Section C: Motivation for application	19
Section D: Previous experience.....	27
Section E: Contacts	38
Section F: Sociodemographics	44
Section G: Parents.....	54
Section H: Thanks.....	68
End message	69
Publication bibliography.....	70
Appendix	i

DESCRIPTION

This English questionnaire is based on the German version (Geisler 2022). The present questionnaire was used in 2020 to survey applicants for the bachelor's study program in fine arts at the German Art Academy "Hochschule für bildende Künste Hamburg" (HFBK). The questions focused on information about the application and application motivation, previous artistic experience and contacts in the art field. In combination with the questioning of socio-demographic variables, social inequalities in the application to study fine arts in Germany could be exemplarily researched.

The first version of the German questionnaire was developed together with Doerte Hinrichsen and tested with cognitive pretests (Geisler and Hinrichsen 2021 (unpublished); Geisler 2021). The questionnaire construction was based on the questionnaires used in the survey of applicants at the Institute of Fine Arts at the Vienna Academy of Fine Arts "Akademie der bildenden Künste Wien" (Rothmüller 2010) and in the survey of graduates at the HFBK Hamburg (Lohmann and Peter 2020). Further development of the questionnaire, field pretest, implementation and evaluation of the survey took place in the context of the following master thesis:

Geisler, Helena (2021): Rückenwind oder Gegenwind beim Zugang zum Kunststudium? Durchführung und Analyse einer Studienbewerber*innen-Befragung an der Hochschule für bildende Künste Hamburg. Master thesis accepted at the Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences and the Faculty of Education, University of Hamburg, Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences. <https://katalogplus.sub.uni-hamburg.de/vufind/Record/1811938515?rank=1>.

This questionnaire is based on the questionnaire printed in the appendix of the master's thesis and is supplemented with references to the underlying questions of the surveys by (Rothmüller 2010) and (Lohmann and Peter 2020). For better clarity, the questions have been numbered.

Of the 830 persons who applied for the BA Fine Arts at the HFBK Hamburg in the winter semester 2020/21, 591 agreed to be invited to the survey by mail (Geisler 2021). In the one-week field phase, 273 applicants started the questionnaire, and 213 answered it completely, with a median time of about 14 min (Geisler 2021). In a follow-up survey, the application result was asked. The data from both surveys were linked by a number that was displayed to the participants in the first survey and that they entered again in the follow-up survey. In the second survey, 124 persons participated, of which 53 cases could be matched to the first survey (Geisler 2021).

The financial costs for printing the invitation flyer for the field pretest, programming the survey with LimeSurvey, and English translation of the questionnaire were covered by HFBK Hamburg (Geisler 2021). HFBK Hamburg also provided organizational support by including the note about the survey in their online application and arranged for the check of the data protection notice (Geisler 2021).

The [appendix](#) provides an overview of the development of the questionnaire over time.

QUESTIONNAIRE STRUCTURE

Table 1 Overview of the sections of the questionnaire

Section name / Question name	Section title / Question title
Section A	Matching
Question 1	Number for matching
Question 2	Specification number
Section B	Application
Question 3	Departments
Question 4	Previous application
Question 4a	<i>Portfolio review</i>
Question 4b	<i>Selection interview</i>
Question 5	HFBK visit
Question 5a	<i>Occasion</i>
Question 6	Support
Question 6a	<i>Professional support</i>
Question 6b	<i>Financial support</i>
Section C	Motivation for application
Question 7	Decision for fine arts
Question 8	Other decision fine arts
Question 8a	<i>Explanation decision fine arts</i>
Question 9	Decision for HFBK
Question 10	Other decision HFBK
Question 10a	<i>Explanation decision HFBK</i>
Section D	Previous experience
Question 11	Type of previous experience
Question 11a	<i>Courses</i>
Question 11b	<i>Vocational training</i>
Question 12	Competitions

Question 12a	Prices
Question 12b	Level
Question 13	Presentations
Question 13a	Area
Question 14	Own work
Question 14a	Experience through work
Question 14b	Type of work experience
Section E	Contacts
Question 15	Work fine arts
Question 15a	Group work fine arts
Question 15b	Family work fine arts
Question 16	Fine arts studies
Question 16a	Group fine arts studies
Question 16b	Family fine arts studies
Section F	Sociodemographics
Question 17	Age
Question 18	Gender
Question 19	Educational degree
Question 20	Change in educational degree
Question 20a	Future degree
Question 21	First language
Question 22	Country of growing up
Question 23	Moving for study
Question 23a	Moving from country
Section G	Parents
Question 24	Number of parents
Question 24a	Influence
Question 25a	Gender parent 1
Question 25b	Gender parent 2

Question 26a	<i>Educational qualification parent 1</i>
Question 26b	<i>Educational qualification parent 2</i>
Question 27a	<i>German citizenship parent 1</i>
Question 27b	<i>German citizenship parent 2</i>
Question 28a	<i>Other nationalities parent 1</i>
Question 28b	<i>Other nationalities parent 2</i>
Question 29a	<i>Occupation parent 1</i>
Question 29b	<i>Occupation parent 2</i>
Section H	Thanks
Question 30	Comments questionnaire

NOTICE IN THE ONLINE APPLICATION

We would like to ask you to take part in our online survey in [time period] in order to evaluate the quality of our selection procedure. The survey is voluntary, anonymous and has no influence on your selection result.

The information you give in the online survey will not be linked to your person in any way. We would appreciate it if you help us to contribute to a transparent and non-discriminatory selection procedure by participating in the online survey.

This consent is voluntary and can be cancelled at any time without giving reasons. In this case, please contact the following mailbox: [mailaddress]

I agree to receive the invitation to this online survey via my e-mail address.

[Yes|No]

WELCOME MESSAGE

Dear Fine Arts applicants,

I invite you to take part in an anonymous survey of HFBK Hamburg Fine Arts applicants!

You can fill out the following anonymous online questionnaire until [date], which will take about 15 minutes.

Independent of the admissions procedure, I am investigating the application procedure for the Bachelor study programme "Fine Arts" at the HFBK Hamburg as part of my Master's thesis.

I would be happy about your participation in the survey!

Helena Geisler

PRIVACY POLICY

All responses are voluntary and will be gathered anonymously. I will not log your IP address or save referrer URLs. The survey is not based on case evaluation, but will use an aggregated statistical evaluation. Answers cannot be traced back and matched to an individual respondent. Your data will not be passed on to third parties.

Please address any questions regarding the collection, processing and use of your data and request for information about the content of the survey to: Helena Geisler, e-mail: [e-mail-address]

SECTION A: MATCHING

SECTION TEXT

Please write down the number below for your voluntary feedback in May.

In May of this year, you will have the opportunity to voluntarily report back the result of your application via a link. When doing so, I would ask you to state the number mentioned below. It was generated automatically and it is individual for all participants. This allows me to anonymously match your answers to this questionnaire with your voluntary response on the result of your application in May.

QUESTION 1: NUMBER FOR MATCHING

PROGRAMMING

Short text field; show saved ID (SID) as question text [enables linkage to follow-up questionnaire].

FILTER

–

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please write down the displayed number or take a screenshot. You will need the number in May of this year.

QUESTION TEXT

{SAVEDID}

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

–

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

(8888) nicht abgefragt [not queried]

REFERENCES

–

QUESTION 2: SPECIFICATION NUMBER

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

-

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) Yes, I wrote down the displayed number for my voluntary feedback in May.
 - (2) No number is displayed to me.
 - (3) Other
-

REFERENCES

-

SECTION B: APPLICATION

SECTION TEXT

We start with questions about your application at the Hochschule für bildende Künste Hamburg (HFBK):

QUESTION 3: DEPARTMENT

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields and “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

–

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

To which department at the HFBK have you made an application this year?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

–

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) Stage Design
- (2) Design
- (3) Film
- (4) Sculpture – Painting/Drawing – Time-Based Media
- (5) Graphic Art/Typography/Photography
- (6) Other (please state): ____

Text

REFERENCES

–

QUESTION 4: PREVIOUS APPLICATION

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

Have you made previous applications (before 2020) to study Fine Arts?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 No
 - 02 Yes, at the HFBK
 - 03 Yes, at (an) other university(ies) of art / art academy(ies) / university(ies) of applied science
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Haben Sie sich schon einmal an einer Kunstuniversität beworben?
 - o Nein
 - o Ja, an der Akademie der Bildenden Künste
 - o Ja, an einer anderen Kunstuniversität
-

QUESTION 4 A: PORTFOLIO REVIEW

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

If Q4_02=1 or Q4_03 =1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes: Have you submitted your own works of art (e.g. as a folder or portfolio) at least once in previous applications?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 4 B: SELECTION INTERVIEW

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

If Q4_02=1 or Q4_03 =1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

Did you have a personal selection interview with members of the teaching staff in previous applications?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 5: HFBK VISIT

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

Have you already visited the HFBK personally before your online application from this year?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 5 A: OCCASION

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question, "other"-option with short text field

FILTER

If Q5=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes: At which opportunity?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Annual Exhibition / Graduate Show at the HFBK
 - 02 Information event for those who are interested in studying at the HFBK
(„Studieninformationstag“)
 - 03 Advice Service for Study Applicants
 - 04 Self-organized visit
 - 05 Other (please state): ____
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
- (1) Gewählt [Selected]

Text

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 6: SUPPORT

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

–

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

Have you been supported professionally or financially by other people in your application to the HFBK?

(For example, feedback on the portfolio or payment for work materials/courses etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 No
 - 02 Yes, I got professional support (*e.g. feedback on the portfolio*)
 - 03 Yes, I got financial support (*e.g. payment for work materials/courses*)
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

–

QUESTION 6 A: PROFESSIONAL SUPPORT

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q6_02=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

People from which area did support you professionally in your application?

(Professional support e.g. through feedback on the application portfolio etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Persons from the family (siblings, parents, grandparents) (*By family is meant the biological family as well as for example the adoptive/nursing and patchwork family etc.*)
 - 02 Friends / acquaintances / other relatives
 - 03 Unrelated persons from the field of fine arts (*e.g. heads of non-school art courses, art professors etc.*)
 - 04 Other persons
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Haben Sie Ihre Arbeiten in der Mappe vor der Prüfung jemandem gezeigt und sich so Rückmeldungen geholt?
 - Nein, niemand
 - Ja, anderen Kunststudierenden
 - Ja, meinen FreundInnen / meiner Familie
 - Ja, ProfessorInnen / Lehrenden
 - Ja, bei einem Klassenbesuch
 - Ja, KünstlerInnen
 - Ja, anderen

QUESTION 6 B: FINANCIAL SUPPORT

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q6_03=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

People from which area did support you financially in your application to the HFBK?

(Financial support e.g. through payment for work materials/courses, etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Persons from the family (siblings, parents, grandparents) (*By family is meant the biological family as well as for example the adoptive/nursing and patchwork family etc.*)
 - 02 Friends / acquaintances / other relatives
 - 03 Unrelated persons from the field of fine arts (e.g. heads of non-school art courses, art professors etc.)
 - 04 Other persons
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

–

SECTION C: MOTIVATION FOR APPLICATION

SECTION TEXT

Now follow questions about how important certain aspects were to you in your decision to apply.

QUESTION 7: DECISION FOR FINE ARTS

PROGRAMMING

Scale question, matrix 4 columns with heading

FILTER

–

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select whether the aspects mentioned were “Not important at all/Less important/Quite important/Very important” in your decision to apply to study art.

QUESTION TEXT

How important were the following aspects in your decision to apply to study art?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 My manual-creative skills
- 02 My skills in the development of ideas in the artistic area
- 03 Visits of art exhibitions / demonstrations / presentations
- 04 The desire to become an artist / designer / film maker etc.
- 05 A wish to develop artistic-manual techniques
- 06 The wish to present own works of art
- 07 The wish to learn about the works of art of other students of art
- 08 The wish to learn about the works of art of other artists / designers / film makers etc.
- 09 The wish to talk about theory (e.g. art history / the philosophy of art)
- 10 The opportunity to improve earning potential by studying
- 11 The opportunity to make contacts in the art field
- 12 The opportunity to establish yourself in the profession (e.g. art market / film business etc.)
- 13 The pleasure of art
- 14 The need to be creative
- 15 My desire to realize myself
- 16 Seeking to change society through art/design/film etc.

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) Not important at all
- (2) Less important
- (3) Quite important
- (4) Very important

REFERENCES

- Cf. on anti-economic motives for choosing a study program 5.1.7 in Saner et al. 2022
- Lohmann and Peter 2020: In welchem Maße haben Sie durch das Studium an der HFBK folgende Kenntnisse und Fähigkeiten erworben?
 - Beherrschung künstlerischer Mittel und Techniken
 - Fähigkeit, künstlerische Ideen und Lösungen zu entwickeln
 - Theoretisches Wissen (etwa zu Kunstgeschichte, ästhetischer Theorie, Kunstvermittlung)
 - Fähigkeit zur künstlerischen Zusammenarbeit
 - Künstlerische Ausdrucksfähigkeit
 - Fähigkeit, eine eigene unabhängige künstlerische Position zu entwickeln
 - Fähigkeit zum konzeptionellen Denken
 - Fähigkeit zum projektbezogenen, zielorientierten Arbeiten
 - Fähigkeit, die eigene Arbeit öffentlich zu präsentieren

QUESTION 8: OTHER DECISION FINE ARTS

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Are there any other aspects that were very important for your decision to apply to study art in general?

(Aspects that specifically influenced your decision to apply to the HFBK can be selected in a following question.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 8 A: EXPLANATION DECISION FINE ARTS

PROGRAMMING

Short text field

FILTER

If Q8=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

-

QUESTION TEXT

If yes, which?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

Text

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 9: DECISION FOR HFBK

PROGRAMMING

Scale question, matrix 5 columns with heading

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select whether the aspects mentioned were “Not important at all/Less important/Quite important/Very important” for your application especially at the HFBK, select “I did not know” if you were not aware of the aspects during your application.

QUESTION TEXT

How important were the following aspects for your application especially at the HFBK?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 The attractiveness of the city Hamburg
 - 02 Friends/aquaintances who live in Hamburg
 - 03 The specifics of the HFBK application deadlines
 - 04 The reputation of the HFBK department to which you have applied this year (e.g. Painting/Drawing; Film; Stage Design etc.)
 - 05 The reputation of the study programme at the HFBK generally
 - 06 Artistic / theoretical works by the teaching staff at the HFBK
 - 07 Artistic / theoretical works by former HFBK students
 - 08 The possibility to develop an own artistic position (without given tasks)
 - 09 The workshop facilities at the HFBK (e.g. introductory course in the Ceramics Workshop / Wood Workshop etc.)
 - 10 The range of academic theory taught at the HFBK (e.g. art science/design theory etc.)
 - 11 Freedom in the organisation of studying (e.g. there is no fixed structure with consecutive consents)
 - 12 The opportunity to select and combine different departments (e.g. Painting/Drawing and Film; Stage Design and Design etc.)
 - 13 The co-operation of the HFBK with international Art universities
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) Not important at all
 - (2) Less important
 - (3) Quite important
 - (4) Very important
- (777) I did not know
-

REFERENCES

- Lohmann and Peter 2020: Wie wichtig waren folgende Aspekte bei Ihrer Entscheidung für ein Studium an der HFBK?
 - Ruf der Hochschule
 - Profil des Studiengangs
 - Werke und Schaffen bisheriger HFBK-Absolventen bzw. HFBK-Absolventinnen
 - Werke und Schaffen von HFBK-Lehrenden
 - Persönlicher Kontakt zu HFBK-Lehrenden
 - Persönlicher Kontakt zu HFBK-Studierenden
 - Bewerbungsfristen
 - Nähe zur Familie
 - Nähe zu Partner/-in oder zum Freundeskreis
 - Attraktivität der Stadt Hamburg

QUESTION 10: OTHER DECISION HFBK

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Were there further aspects that were very important for your decision to apply especially at the HFBK to study Fine Arts?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 10 A: EXPLANATION DECISION HFBK

PROGRAMMING

Short text field

FILTER

If Q10=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

-

QUESTION TEXT

If yes, which aspects?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

Text

REFERENCES

-

SECTION D: PREVIOUS EXPERIENCE

SECTION TEXT

Thank you, the following are questions regarding previous artistic experience.

REFERENCES:

- Cf. Bourdieu 2005, pp. 53–63; Rothmüller 2010, p. 131; Saner et al. 2022, p. 202, 209, 278

QUESTION 11: TYPE OF PREVIOUS EXPERIENCE

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question and “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

–

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

Have you already gathered artistic experience?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 No
- 02 Yes, through independent artistic work without courses etc.
- 03 Yes, from visiting art exhibitions / demonstrations / presentations etc.
- 04 Yes, from courses at or outside school
- 05 Yes, through training / study (in a company/college/university etc.)
- 06 Other (please state): __

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
- (1) Gewählt [Selected]

Text

REFERENCES

–

QUESTION 11 A: COURSES

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q11_04=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes, courses in which context?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- o1 In a school context (*e.g. Art club, major courses*)
 - o2 In a non-school context (*e.g. life drawing course, portfolio preparation course etc.*)
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 11 B: VOCATIONAL TRAINING

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q11_05=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes, which training/study?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Company training (*handicraft, e.g. goldsmith, carpenter etc.*)
 - 02 School training (*e.g. Fashion Design at fashion school etc.*)
 - 03 Artistic study (*e.g. Illustration, Photography, Fine Arts*)
 - 04 Art theory studies (*e.g. art history, theatre studies etc.*)
 - 05 Other
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Haben Sie bereits eine künstlerische Ausbildung begonnen oder abgeschlossen?
 - Nein
 - Ja, Kurse
 - Ja, eine schulische Vor-/Ausbildung im künstlerisch-kreativen Bereich (z. Bsp. AHS mit bildnerischem Schwerpunkt, HTL, Modeschule)
 - Ja, ein Kolleg im künstlerisch-kreativen Bereich
 - Ja, eine Fachhochschule im künstlerisch-kreativen Bereich
 - Ja, ein Studium an einer Kunstuniversität

QUESTION 12: COMPETITIONS

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Have you ever participated in competitions with your own artwork/artistic works?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 12 A: PRICES

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

If Q12=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes: Have you won a prize at least once?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

(0) No

(1) Yes

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 12 B: LEVEL

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q12a=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

At what level did you win (an) award(s)?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 At regional level
 - 02 At national level
 - 03 At international level
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 13: PRESENTATIONS

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

–

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Have you displayed your work publically within the last twelve months?

(Within the scope of an exhibition/demonstrations/presentations, commissioned work, work on digital platforms or Streetart etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

–

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

(0) No

(1) Yes

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Haben Sie selbst bereits Ihre Arbeiten öffentlich gezeigt (Ausstellung, Screening, usw.)?
 - Nein
 - Ja, 1–2 mal
 - Ja, 3 mal oder öfter
-

QUESTION 13 A: AREA

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q13=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes, in which area have you exhibited your artistic work?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Public group exhibitions / demonstrations / presentations
 - 02 Public individual exhibitions / demonstrations / presentations
 - 03 Publicly visible commissioned work (e.g. poster/wall design, stage design etc.)
 - 04 On the Internet on digital platforms (e.g. Instagram, DeviantArt etc.)
 - 05 Streetart in public space
 - 06 Other
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 14: OWN WORK

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Have you worked within the Fine Arts sector within the last twelve months?

(e.g. within the scope of work experience/employment/comissioned work etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Haben Sie bereits in einem künstlerischen Projekt mitgearbeitet oder ein Praktikum im Kunstbereich gemacht?
 - o Nein
 - o Ja, 1-2 mal
 - o Ja, 3 mal oder öfter

QUESTION 14 A: EXPERIENCE THROUGH WORK

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

If Q14=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes: Have you gained previous artistic experience through this?

(e.g. theoretical knowledge, craft skills or contacts in the field of fine arts etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

(0) No

(1) Yes

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 14 B: TYPE OF WORK EXPERIENCE

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question and “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

If Q14a=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes: Which ones?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Theoretical knowledge
 - 02 Craft skills
 - 03 Contacts in the field of fine arts
 - 04 Other (please state): ____
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
- (1) Gewählt [Selected]

Text

REFERENCES

-

SECTION E: CONTACTS

SECTION TEXT

The following are questions regarding your personal contacts in the areas of art and culture:

QUESTION 15: WORK FINE ARTS

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

–

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Does or has anyone within your personal network (family, friends, acquaintances, other relations) have experience of work in the Fine Arts area?

(e.g. within the scope of internship / employment / commissioned work etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

–

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Kennen Sie jemand außerhalb Ihrer Familie persönlich, der oder die Kunst zum Beruf gemacht hat bzw. im Kunstfeld tätig ist (z. Bsp. KünstlerIn, KunstvermittlerIn, KuratorIn, usw.)?
 - Nein
 - Ja, 1–2 Personen
 - Ja, 3 oder mehr Personen
-

QUESTION 15 A: GROUP WORK FINE ARTS

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q15=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes, who does or has have experiences of work in the Fine Arts area?

(e.g. within the scope of internship / employment / commissioned work etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Person(s) from your immediate family (siblings/parents/grandparents) (*By family is meant the biological family as well as for example the adoptive/nursing and patchwork family etc.*)
 - 02 Friends/ acquaintances / other relations
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Arbeitet jemand aus Ihrer Familie im Kunst- und Kulturbereich?
 - Nein
 - Ja, 1–2 Personen
 - Ja, 3 oder mehr Personen
-

QUESTION 15 B: FAMILY WORK FINE ARTS

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q15a_01=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

Who of your family (siblings/parents/grandparents) does or has have experiences of work in the Fine Arts area?

(By family is meant the biological family as well as for example the adoptive/nursing and patchwork family etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Sibling(s)
 - 02 Parent(s)
 - 03 Grandparent(s)
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

- Lohmann and Peter 2020: Sind oder waren Ihre Eltern künstlerisch tätig?
 - Ja, mein Vater
 - Ja, meine Mutter
 - Ja, beide
 - Nein
-

QUESTION 16: FINE ARTS STUDIES

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Does or has anyone from your personal network (family, friends, acquaintances, other relations) have experience of study at a university of art or academy of art?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Studieren oder studierten FreundInnen oder Bekannte von Ihnen auf der Akademie?
 - o Nein
 - o Ja, 1-2 Personen
 - o Ja, 3 oder mehr Personen

QUESTION 16 A: GROUP FINE ARTS STUDIES

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q16=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes, who does or has have experiences of study at a universtiy of art or academy of art?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Persons from your immediate family (siblings, parents, grandparents) (*By family is meant the biological family as well as for example the adoptive/nursing and patchwork family etc.*)
 - 02 Friends / acquaintances / other relations
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

–

QUESTION 16 B: FAMILY FINE ARTS STUDIES

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question

FILTER

If Q16a_01=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

Who of your family (siblings/parents/grandparents) does or has have experiences of study at a university of art or academy of art?

(By family is meant the biological family as well as for example the adoptive/nursing and patchwork family etc.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Sibling(s)
 - 02 Parent(s)
 - 03 Grandparent(s)
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
 - (1) Gewählt [Selected]
-

REFERENCES

-

SECTION F: SOCIODEMOGRAPHICS

SECTION TEXT

Now follow questions about yourself in order to be able to assign you to social groups.

These questions help to evaluate the answers to the questions asked so far according to characteristics that describe social groups. The data will not be evaluated for your person under any circumstances, but only for groups to which you can be assigned, for example, according to your age group or origin. Your anonymity is preserved by the evaluation in groups.

QUESTION 17: AGE

PROGRAMMING

Number input

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

-

QUESTION TEXT

Please state your age (in years):

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

Number

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 18: GENDER

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Please state your gender.

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) Male
 - (2) Female
 - (3) Diverse
-

REFERENCES

- Lohmann and Peter 2020: Welches Geschlecht haben Sie?
 - o Männlich
 - o Weiblich
 - o Divers
- Rothmüller 2010: Geschlecht: ____

QUESTION 19: EDUCATIONAL DEGREE

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields, “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

What is currently the highest educational qualification that you hold?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) Do not (yet) have a school leaving certificate
- (2) Certificate of Secondary Education
- (3) General Certificate of Secondary Education
- (4) University Entrance Qualification
- (5) Bachelor’s degree
- (6) Master’s degree
- (7) Doctoral qualification
- (8) Other (please state): ____

Text

REFERENCES

- Lohmann and Peter 2020: Welchen höchsten allgemeinbildenden Schulabschluss haben Sie?
 - o Schule beendet ohne Abschluss
 - o Volks-/Hauptschulabschluss (DDR: 8. Klasse POS)
 - o Mittlere Reife, Realschulabschluss (DDR: 10. Klasse POS)
 - o Fachhochschulreife (Abschluss einer Fachoberschule etc.)
 - o Abitur/Hochschulreife (DDR: EOS)
 - o Einen anderen Abschluss, und zwar: ____
- Rothmüller 2010: Welche höchste Ausbildung haben Sie *abgeschlossen*?
 - o Pflichtschule (od. weiterführende Ausbildung abgebrochen)
 - o Lehre/Berufsschule
 - o Berufsbildende Mittlere Schule (BMS)
 - o Meisterprüfung
 - o Allgemeinbildende Höhere Schule (AHS)
 - o Berufsbildende Höhere Schule (BHS), Kolleg,
 - o Akademie (PädAk, SozAk, u. ä.)

- Universität, Fachhochschule
 - Andere: _____
- UNESCO and UIS 2012

QUESTION 20: CHANGE IN EDUCATIONAL DEGREE

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Do you expect to hold another highest educational qualification in October 2020?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
 - (1) Yes
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 20 A: FUTURE DEGREE

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields, “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

If Q20=1

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes, which?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (2) Certificate of Secondary Education
- (3) General Certificate of Secondary Education
- (4) University Entrance Qualification
- (5) Bachelor’s degree
- (6) Master’s degree
- (7) Doctoral qualification
- (8) Other (please state): ____

Text

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 21: FIRST LANGUAGE

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question with comments

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

-

QUESTION TEXT

What is your native language (the first language which you acquired in your early childhood)?

(If you grew up bi or multi-lingual, please specify multiple languages.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 German as first language (*do not comment this choice*) ____
- 02 Other first-language (please state): ____
- 03 Other first-language (because you grew up bi-lingual) (please state): ____
- 04 other first-language (because you grew up multilingual) (please state): ____

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
- (1) Gewählt [Selected]

Text

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010 (132): Erstsprache(n):
 - o Deutsch
 - o Български език/Bălgarski esik
 - o Bosanski jezik
 - o Chinesisch
 - o English
 - o Hrvatski jezik
 - o Italiano
 - o Magyar nyelv
 - o Српски/Srpski
 - o Slovenščina
 - o Andere: ____

QUESTION 22: COUNTRY OF GROWING UP

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question with comments

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

-

QUESTION TEXT

In which country did you spend the *greatest amount* of time up to your 18th birthday?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Germany (*do not comment this choice*) ____
 - 02 Other country (please state): ____
 - 03 Other country (in which you have lived for the same amount of time) (please state): ____
 - 04 I have lived in more than two countries for the same amount of time (*do not comment this choice*)

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
- (1) Gewählt [Selected]

Text

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 23: MOVING FOR STUDY

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

-

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Would you move to Hamburg to study at the HFBK?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) No
- (1) Yes
- (2) I already live in Hamburg

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 23 A: MOVING FROM COUNTRY

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields, “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

If Q23=3

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

If yes, from which country do you plan to move?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) From Germany
- (2) From another country (please state): ____

Text

REFERENCES

-

SECTION G: PARENTS

SECTION TEXT

To conclude, questions about your parents (or other people with responsibility for your growing up).

At the end of this survey, please answer the following questions about your parents (or other people who have taken practical responsibility for your growing up). These questions will also help to evaluate your answers according to characteristics that describe social groups. This is important so that this survey can evaluate which social groups participate in the HFBK application process.

QUESTION 24: NUMBER OF PARENTS

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields, “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

–

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

How many parents have influenced your growing up until your 18th birthday?

(Meant are both biological parents as well as e.g. adoptive/nursing/stepparents.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

–

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) One parent
- (2) Two parents
- (3) More than two parents
- (4) Other (please state): ____

Text

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Angaben zu den Eltern:
 - Habe beide Eltern
 - Habe nur einen Elternteil (*überspringen Sie bitte die Fragen zum 2. Elternteil*)
 - Elternlos (*beantworten Sie wenn möglich folgende Fragen für die Person, bei der Sie die längste Zeit aufgewachsen sind*)

QUESTION 24 A: INFLUENCE

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

If Q24=3

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

How many of these persons were most influential?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) One
 - (2) Two
 - (3) More than two
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 25 A: GENDER PARENT 1

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

If Q24=1 or Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=1 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose only one of the following:

QUESTION TEXT

Please select the gender of one parent. This parent will be called first parent in the following questions.

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) Male
 - (2) Female
 - (3) Diverse
-

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Geschlecht: ____

QUESTION 25 B: GENDER PARENT 2

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

If Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

Please select the gender of your second parent and always refer first to your first parent and then to this second parent.

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) Male
 - (2) Female
 - (3) Diverse
-

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 26 A: EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION PARENT 1

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields, “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

If Q24=1 or Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=1 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2:

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

Please select the highest educational qualification of your first parent.

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

–

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) No school qualification
- (2) Certificate of Secondary Education
- (3) General Certificate of Secondary Education
- (4) University Entrance Qualification
- (5) Bachelor’s degree
- (6) Master’s degree
- (7) Doctoral qualification

(777) I do not know

(8) Other (please state): ____

Text

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Höchste abgeschlossene Ausbildung:
 - Pflichtschule (oder weiterführende Ausbildung abgebrochen)
 - Lehre/Berufsschule
 - Berufsbildende Mittlere Schule (BMS)
 - Meisterprüfung
 - Allgemeinbildende Höhere Schule (AHS)
 - Berufsbildende Höhere Schule (BHS), Kolleg
 - Akademie (PädAk, SozAk, u. ä.)
 - Universität, Fachhochschule
 - Andere: ____
 - Weiß ich nicht

- Lohmann and Peter 2020: Welchen höchsten allgemeinbildenden Schulabschluss hat Ihr Vater/Ihre Mutter erworben?
 - Keinen Schulabschluss
 - Volks-/Hauptschulabschluss (DDR: 8. Klasse POS)
 - Mittlere Reife, Realschulabschluss (DDR: 10. Klasse POS)
 - Abitur/Hochschulreife (DDR: EOS), Fachhochschulreife
 - Anderen Schulabschluss
 - Weiß nicht

- Hat Ihr Vater/Ihre Mutter eine berufliche Ausbildung oder ein Studium abgeschlossen?
 - Nein, keine abgeschlossene Ausbildung
 - Ja, berufliche Ausbildung
 - Ja, (Fach-)Hochschulstudium
 - Weiß nicht
- UNESCO and UIS 2012

QUESTION 26 B: EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION PARENT 2

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields, “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

If Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

Please select the highest educational qualification of your second parent.

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (1) No school qualification
- (2) Certificate of Secondary Education
- (3) General Certificate of Secondary Education
- (4) University Entrance Qualification
- (5) Bachelor’s degree
- (6) Master’s degree
- (7) Doctoral qualification

(777) I do not know

(8) Other (please state): ____

Text

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 27 A: GERMAN CITIZENSHIP PARENT 1

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

If Q24=1 or Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=1 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

Please indicate whether or not your first legal guardian has German citizenship.

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

(0) No

(1) Yes

(777) I do not know

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 27 B: GERMAN CITIZENSHIP PARENT 2

PROGRAMMING

Single Choice Question, List of option fields

FILTER

If Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please select only one of the following answers:

QUESTION TEXT

Please indicate whether or not your *second* legal guardian has German citizenship.

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

(0) No

(1) Yes

(777) I do not know

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 28 A: OTHER NATIONALITIES PARENT 1

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question with comments

FILTER

If Q24=1 or Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=1 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

Does your first legal guardian hold (an)other/further nationality(ies)?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 No (do not comment this choice) ____
 - 02 Yes (please state): ____
 - 03 Yes, one more (please state): ____
 - 04 I do not know (do not comment this choice): ____
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
- (1) Gewählt [Selected]

- (777) Weiß ich nicht [I do not know]

Text

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: StaatsbürgerInnenschaft:
 - Österreich
 - EU-StaatsbürgerInnenschaft: ____
 - Andere StaatsbürgerInnenschaft: ____
 - Staatenlos
 - DoppelstaatsbürgerInnenschaft: ____

QUESTION 28 B: OTHER NATIONALITIES PARENT 2

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question with comments

FILTER

If Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

Does your *second* legal guardian hold (an)other / further nationality(ies)?

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 No (*do not comment this choice*) ____
 - 02 Yes (*please state*): ____
 - 03 Yes, one more (*please state*): ____
 - 04 I do not know (*do not comment this choice*): ____
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

- (0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]
- (1) Gewählt [Selected]

- (777) Weiß ich nicht [I do not know]

Text

REFERENCES

-

QUESTION 29 A: OCCUPATION PARENT 1

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question and “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

If Q24=1 or Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=1 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

What is your first legal guardian's occupation?

(If currently no longer employed, please state the last occupation.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Unpaid work in the home
- 02 Unqualified worker
- 03 Qualified or supervisory worker
- 04 Salaried without management responsibilities
- 05 Salaried with management responsibilities
- 06 Lower or middle grade civil servant
- 07 Senior grade civil servant
- 08 Self-employed without employees or with up to 4 company employees
- 09 Self-employed with 5 or more company employees
- 10 I do not know
- 11 Other (please state): ____

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

(0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]

(1) Gewählt [Selected]

(777) Weiß ich nicht [I do not know]

Text

REFERENCES

- Rothmüller 2010: Beruf (wenn aktuell nicht oder nicht mehr berufstätig, geben Sie bitte die letzte Berufsposition an):
 - Angestellte/r, Beamter/Beamtin ohne Leitungsfunktion
 - Angestellte/r, Beamter/Beamtin mit Leitungsfunktion
 - Freiberufler/in (ÄrztIn, JuristIn, KünstlerIn, WissenschaftlerIn, usw.)
 - Arbeiter/in
 - Mithelfend im Familienbetrieb
 - Unternehmer/in, Gewerbetreibende ohne Angestellte

- Unternehmer/in, Gewerbetreibende mit Angestellten
 - Land-/Forstwirt/in
 - Anderer: ____
 - Weiß ich nicht
- Statistisches Bundesamt 2019
- International Labour Office 2022

QUESTION 29 B: OCCUPATION PARENT 2

PROGRAMMING

Multiple Choice Question and “other”-option with short text field

FILTER

If Q24=2 or Q24=3 and Q24a=2

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Please choose all that apply:

QUESTION TEXT

What is your second legal guardian's occupation?

(If currently no longer employed, please state the last occupation.)

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

- 01 Unpaid work in the home
 - 02 Unqualified worker
 - 03 Qualified or supervisory worker
 - 04 Salaried without management responsibilities
 - 05 Salaried with management responsibilities
 - 06 Lower or middle grade civil servant
 - 07 Senior grade civil servant
 - 08 Self-employed without employees or with up to 4 company employees
 - 09 Self-employed with 5 or more company employees
 - 10 I do not know
 - 11 Other (please state): ____
-

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

(0) Nicht gewählt [Not selected]

(1) Gewählt [Selected]

(777) Weiß ich nicht [I do not know]

Text

REFERENCES

–

SECTION H: THANKS

SECTION TEXT

That was the last question. Thank you for your help!

QUESTION 30: COMMENTS QUESTIONNAIRE

PROGRAMMING

Long text field, show saved ID (SID) as question text [enables linkage to follow-up questionnaire]

FILTER

–

NOTE FOR PARTICIPANTS

–

QUESTION TEXT

Once again, please note that you should use the following number in your voluntary response in May 2020: {SAVEDID}

Please keep the number in a safe place.

Here you also have the opportunity for comments or suggestions to the questionnaire.

Hier haben Sie außerdem haben Sie die Möglichkeit für Hinweise oder Anmerkungen zum Fragebogen.

For example, you can mention important aspects for the decision to study fine arts which have not been taken into account or have not been sufficiently considered.

SUBQUESTIONTEXT

–

CODING AND RESPONSE OPTIONS

Text

REFERENCES

- Lohmann and Peter 2020: Das war unsere letzte Frage. Gibt es von Ihrer Seite noch etwas, das Sie zu unserer Umfrage sagen möchten? ____
- Rothmüller 2010: Falls Sie uns noch etwas bezogen auf die Evaluierung der Zulassungsprüfung mitteilen möchten, nutzen Sie bitte die folgenden Zeilen: ____

END MESSAGE

Thank you very much for your details and good luck for your future!

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APPENDIX

Table 2 Overview questionnaire construction and data collection (cf. timetable application procedure HFBK Hamburg and data collection: (Geisler 2021))

Version	Period	Milestone	Comments
1 (Geisler 2021))	04/2019 – 11/2019	Questionnaire construction based on the questionnaire by Rothmüller 2010	In collaboration with Doerte Hinrichsen, in the context of the research workshop Educational Science. Support by “Servicestelle empirische Forschungsmethoden“ (Dr. Rau) and Prof. Lohmann
	12/2019– 01/2020	Cognitive pretesting with first semester students and prospective students	Appointment made with 6 persons, after two cancellations interviews conducted with 4 persons, in cooperation with Doerte Hinrichsen, in the context of the research workshop Educational Science. Support by Equal Opportunity Officer HFBK (Prof. Mutter) for contact with first semester students
2 (Geisler 2021)	01/2020	Revision of the questionnaire, English translation of the questionnaire, control of the translation	Translation by translation agency commissioned by HFBK
3 (Geisler 2021)	02/2020	Feldpretest (Feb. 8 to 12, 2020), start on the study information day of the HFBK, revision of the questionnaire	8 prospective students started questionnaire, 6 completed (cf. Geisler 2021, p. 30)
final (Geisler 2021)	03/2020	Survey part 1 (March 23 to 29, 2020)	originally planned period (March 6 to 26, 2020) delayed due to lockdown because of Corona pandemic
	05/2020– 06/2020	Applicant survey part 2	Postponed to end of May, because of measures to contain the pandemic selection interviews postponed.